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Planning the Future of Research & Innovation in the European University Alliance UNITE!

Unite! Open science and innovation strategic roadmap

Deliverable 6.1

Deliverable

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Author(s) – Partner(s)	R. Vicente-Saez (AALTO), A. Rossi (AALTO), R. Gustafsson (AALTO), K. Laakso (AALTO), P. Looman (KTH), F. Cappelluti (POLITO), S. Kurapati (POLITO), S. Rollino (POLITO), S. Tabotta (POLITO), P. Ferrero (POLITO), A. Rapp (TUDa), G. Jagusch (TUDa), J. Windeck (TUDa), A. Legrand (UGA), P. Bressoux (UGA), M.H. Ribeiro (ULISBOA), A. Rovira-Fernandez (UPC)
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Our aim

The ultimate aim of open science should be the informed and extended co-creation of knowledge by all humanity. The goal of this strategic roadmap is to progress towards this aim, by defining a set of objectives and providing recommendations for promoting, developing and implementing university and school level actions, redesigns and incentives for advancing the adoption of open science practices, principles and goals across the universities of the Unite! Alliance. This strategic roadmap describes what actions Unite! Universities should promote to constitute Unite! Alliance as a European engine of open science and innovation by 2023. This strategic roadmap strengthens the development towards the Unite! R&I Agenda.

Our commitment

This strategic roadmap is meant as a guideline for University leaders and regional and national science and innovation policymakers for advancing the opening of science in the Unite! Alliance research systems, for a sustainable economy, society and environment, for a sustainable world. The objectives and recommendations embrace the international framework for policy and practice set up by the [UNESCO Recommendation](#) on how to boost Open Science, approved on 23th November 2021.

Our values and impact

These objectives and recommendations can guide, enhance and foster an open science culture and environment by boosting transparency, accessibility, legitimacy and participation in science among the Unite! research communities of researchers, students, staff, faculty, citizens and partners.

The adoption of open science practices, principles and goals among the Unite! research communities can improve the quality both internal – academic– and external –societal– processes of learning and creation of new knowledge, increasing trust in science, nurturing innovative and entrepreneurial people, and accelerating research and innovation process for finding solutions for the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations.

Why open science and innovation?

Open science is transparent and accessible knowledge, shared and developed through collaborative networks. It involves sharing ideas, data, methods and results with local, national, regional and global collaborative networks of research participants. It also goes beyond this to encompass scientific knowledge produced and used by these collaborative networks.

Science is being reshaped by advances in digital technology and tools, including big data, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, 3D printing and quantum computing, along with open digital and physical infrastructures, including open labs, open libraries, cultural heritage, digital knowledge bases and open university campuses. These technologies and infrastructures have, in turn, allowed researchers to experiment with, develop and adopt new open science practices, principles and goals for tackling grand societal challenges.

Open innovation is the use of purposive inflows and outflows of knowledge to accelerate internal and external innovation. Open science practices for the sharing of knowledge –open data, open access publishing, open protocols, open prototypes– and open science practices for the production of knowledge –transdisciplinary research, participatory design, citizen science, open collaborative tools– have created extraordinary possibilities to this knowledge value creation and transfer process. These practices are expanding not only the “ethos” in science, but also the “ethos” in innovation in universities. Open science practices are transforming science and innovation practices in universities.

Our choices

To support our direction, we suggest five building blocks that best help constitute Unite! Alliance as a European engine of open science and innovation by 2023:

Objective 1. Developing open science policies and open science strategies

Objective 2. Enhancing the opening up of digital and physical infrastructures

Objective 3. Promoting open science support services

Objective 4. Fostering open science in careers

Objective 5. Improving open science competencies

Objective 1. Developing open science policies and open science strategies

Recommendation 1. Unite! Universities should develop or align their open science policies at university level, building on the UNESCO Recommendation on open science and their regional, national and EU policies, to boost a culture of openness across their research communities. These open science policies should define a common set of principles, standards, goals, career evaluation system, incentives and funding for the operationalization of open science at university level.

Recommendation 2. Unite! Universities should promote open science strategies at school level to implement their open science policies. These open science strategies should provide hands-on guidance on how to adopt open sharing and open collaborative science practices, and how to use open digital and physical infrastructures, taking into account the diversity of each research area.

Objective 2. Enhancing the opening up of digital and physical infrastructures

Recommendation 3. Unite! Universities should invest in university level digital infrastructures for the sharing and production of knowledge among their research communities. This university level digital infrastructure should ensure open as possible –ethical and legal– and permanent open scientific knowledge access – data, code, methods, prototypes, results – for everyone. This infrastructure should allow interoperability, guarantee implementing FAIR data principles, and ensure safety and security.

Recommendation 4. Unite! Universities should open their school level physical infrastructures for research, teaching and innovating, for everyone. They should create guidelines about the infrastructures access policies, training requirements and operation the tools and instruments.

Objective 3. Promoting open science support services

Recommendation 5. Unite! Universities should develop university level open science units for supporting their researcher communities along the different stages of the open scientific process. These units should provide seed funding and training in infrastructure, tools and skills that support and incentivise the adoption of open science practices, principles and goals among their research communities.

Recommendation 6. Unite! Universities should promote open science specialists at school level. These specialists should provide technical assistance, with regard to the specificities of each discipline of knowledge, and promote cross-border multi-stakeholder co-creation of knowledge among their research communities.

Objective 4. Fostering open science in careers

Recommendation 7. Unite! Universities should advocate the review of their regional and national research career evaluation systems to align them with the adoption of open science principles, practices and goals. These new career evaluation systems should give recognition to researchers for the co-creation of knowledge among collaborative networks of research participants.

Recommendation 8. Unite! Universities should adopt school level incentives for rewarding research processes and outputs related to the adoption of open science principles, practices and goals.

Objective 5. Improving open science competencies

Recommendation 9. Unite! Universities should promote multilingual open educational resources on open science for the capacity-building of their research communities. These resources should boost the participation in science among their research communities, composed of researchers, students, staff, faculty, citizens and partners.

Recommendation 10. Unite! Universities should open their training in open science infrastructure, tools and skills for everyone. Programmes, courses, MOOCS, workshops, seminars on-demand on open science should be promoted across their research communities and worldwide as a foundation stone of a European open science and innovation university.

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University Network for Innovation,
Technology and Engineering

Annex: Booklet. Unite! open sharing and inviting initiatives

The Bootcamp “What is open in open science?” (June 08-09, 2021) looked at which transformations were ongoing at Unite! Universities with the aim to co-create a common open science and innovation institutional vision for a high impact alliance.

(<https://www.unite-university.eu/whatsnew/unite-staff-gathered-to-define-an-open-science-and-innovation-strategic-roadmap-towards-a-high-impact-alliance>)

This Booklet “Unite! open sharing and inviting initiatives” co-created in May-June 2021, supported mutual learning and identification of good practices during the Bootcamp, on how Unite! Universities were embracing initiatives towards open science.

This Booklet provides a high-level overview of the current adoption of open science practices, principles and goals across Unite! Universities.

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University Network for Innovation,
Technology and Engineering

Booklet

Unite! open sharing and inviting initiatives

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Open sharing initiatives

Aalto

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- A. **Aalto University Open Science and Research Policy**: Aalto University supports open science in its research community and by doing it aims at gaining the benefits of openness: the societal impact of research increases, the speed of innovation grows, the high quality and transparency of science are ensured, and research results are openly accessible in helping to solve global problems. Key pillars:
- **Open access to scientific publications**: (1) Aalto-University aims to publish all publication types according to open access principles and to do so by recommending publishing in open access channels or by parallel publishing (green open access). (2) Aalto University requires that all peer-reviewed scientific articles and conference papers be parallel published (green open access) in the Aalto University repository if this does not conflict with the rights of publishers or other authors. (3) Most doctoral and master's theses are published in an electronic format in the Aalto University repository (4) As a member of the FinELib consortium, Aalto University aims to secure open access agreements or discounts on article processing charges (APCs) with publishers.
 - **Open and FAIR Research Data**: (1) Researchers (incl. doctoral students) and research groups are encouraged to draw up a data management plan (DMP) at the beginning stage of research and update the plan regularly. (2) Data that are linked to research publications and data that are suitable for reuse have to be made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) to the extent beneficial to society after the data creators and collectors have benefitted from the data (the right to primary use of data). (3) Aalto University requires that rights related to research data be defined in agreements.
 - **Open protocols, methods, software codes**: (1) should be shared openly, even when implemented with proprietary tools, to guarantee the transparency and replicability of the data collection and analysis process. (2) There are various suitable licenses (Creative Commons CC BY 4.0, MIT or GNU). The right choice for the license can depend on the philosophy of the researchers as well as on restrictions imposed by any third-party libraries used. (3) When pertinent, it is recommended that the choice of research protocols and analysis methods be pre-registered before beginning data collection and analysis.
- B. **Aalto University digital infrastructure for knowledge sharing**: [ACRIS](#) and [Aaltodoc](#) together form the Aalto publication repository. ACRIS (Research Information System) collects important research and activity information and makes it visible and available in [Research.aalto.fi](#) (public portal) thus improving the impact of Aalto University's scientific and artistic activity. ACRIS facilitates the management of academic merits of researchers and artists by providing a platform for registering scientific and artistic activity, automatically producing a great deal of information to assist researchers, such as data on affiliations and education, Scopus and WOS publications and citations, metrics data on journals, etc. Researchers submit their manuscript to a designated email after which the services upload it to ACRIS where it will be made open access. Manuscripts are transferred to Aaltodoc archive for long-term preservation. A new initiative is to more exhaustively gather and showcase research data metadata in ACRIS.
- C. **Aalto University open science services**: Support to researchers through tailor-made services ([manuscript service](#), [FAIR and open data support](#), [research data management service](#)) [consultations](#), [RDM training](#), or [workshops](#).
- D. **Pionnering open sharing initiatives promoted by researchers (bottom-up approach)**:
- [Aalto Metsähovi Observatory](#) won the Finnish national open science award in 2020 for producing continuously accumulating observational data openly for the use of the national and international research community. For example, it produces solar data, which can be used to prevent disturbances that the sun's activities can potentially cause, e.g. telecommunications.
 - [Research Institute of Measuring and Modeling for the Built Environment \(MeMo\)](#) won the Finnish national open science award in 2019 for promoting new ways of making scientific outputs available to a wider audience in a new kind of 3D experience in plays, films and various performances.

Next steps: Incentives for openness and criteria for evaluation of openness. These are to be defined in the national level collaboration.

KTH

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- Digitalisation policy, KTH, June 2020. <https://www.kth.se/blogs/vicerektorererna/en/2020/06/a-digitalisation-policy-for-the-future/>
- We're just started a process at KTH in formulating a vision and strategy of open science at KTH. It probably will lean on the SUHF (The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions) roadmap to open science (2021): <https://suhf.se/app/uploads/2021/03/REK-2021-1-F%C3%A4rdplan-f%C3%B6r-%C3%B6ppen-vetenskap-SUHF-Antagen-210310-REV-1.pdf>
- Open science and Research Data management - a Canvas course for researchers at KTH, <https://canvas.kth.se/courses/29371>
- Research data guidelines, KTH https://intra.kth.se/polopoly_fs/1.1037531.1608134528!/Guidelines-on-managing-research-data.pdf
- Publication guidelines KTH, in working progress
- Publication repository, Diva
- At the KTH library we're handling all of the publication costs at KTH. This is making it easier for the researchers to publish OA and for us at the library great opportunities to analyze the Open access development at KTH.
- BIBSAM consortium including part of the steering committee: <https://www.kb.se/samverkan-och-utveckling/oppen-tillgang-och-bibsamkonsortiet/open-access-and-bibsam-consortium/bibsam-consortium.html>
- Member of SND - Swedish national data service, <https://snd.gu.se/en>
- DMP Online (data management tool) at KTH, <https://www.kth.se/en/biblioteket/publicera-analysera/hantera-forskningsdata/datahanteringsplan-1.1002818>
- Research data management issues are complex, and require support from different parts of the KTH research support services. The Research data team was created to coordinate research data management issues, create a better infrastructure for research data management at KTH and support researchers establish good data management practices. The Research data team is a collaboration between the KTH Archive, library, IT department, RSO and PDC.
- Open and FAIR Research Data: (1) Researchers (incl. doctoral students) and research groups are encouraged to draw up a data management plan (DMP) at the beginning stage of research and update the plan regularly. (2) Data that are linked to research publications and data that are suitable for reuse have to be made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) to the extent beneficial to society after the data creators and collectors have benefitted from the data (the right to primary use of data). (3) KTH requires that rights related to research data be defined agreements. <https://www.kth.se/en/biblioteket/publicera-analysera/hantera-forskningsdata/forskningsdata-1.1002828>
- Datadriven analysis and follow-up of the research at KTH (<https://abm.sys.kth.se/public/>). <https://abm.sys.kth.se/public/cache/22dc63a37b50987b186ef53b34686e14a25b6d33.html#open-access> . The system is developed open source.

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- Open data flagship – a pilot within SND (Swedish national data service, <https://snd.gu.se/en>)
- Scilifelab - A data-centric approach to Life Science: <https://www.scilifelab.se/data#dataoverview>
- Scilifelab open source projects: <https://www.scilifelab.se/data/open-source-projects>
- Covid-19 data portal: <https://covid19dataportal.se/>
- Data driven life science, <https://www.scilifelab.se/data-driven/>
- KTH Live-In Lab's Datapool is our portal to research data from our Testbeds (buildings) and research results, <https://www.liveinlab.kth.se/en/infrastruktur/datapool/kth-live-in-lab-datapool-1.974702>

Polito

Politecnico has an **Open Access Policy** to scientific publications, which was issued on February 2019 (rector's decree n.87) and came into effect from 1st June 2019.

Politecnico di Torino considers Open Access as an added value for research evaluation processes and recognizes the connection between Open Access and the evaluation process as an essential part of the commitment in supporting Open Access.

In order to implement, promote and support OA, **Politecnico Open Access Commission** was established. The main tasks will be formulating and defining proposals for the promotion of Open Access and evaluating any open access waiver requested by the authors.

Politecnico adopts as Research Institutional Repository **Porto@Iris** where works must be deposited with metadata and fulltext (open access or restricted). The repository Iris is managed by CINECA, an Interuniversity Consortium composed by 2 Italian Ministries, 69 Universities and 26 national public institutions (such as research centers and public hospitals).

Regarding **data**, Politecnico is working on **guidelines** for their management, in line with FAIR principles. Polito short to mid-term strategy is to promote the use of external research data certified repository (<https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository-certified-repositories>) and not to establish an ad hoc infrastructure at its premises. Researchers will be required to deposit just metadata/PID of deposited datasets/software.

Moreover, in order to foster the adoption of Open Science practices Politecnico proposes to **PhD students a course on Open Science**

(https://didattica.polito.it/pls/portal30/gap.pkg_guide.viewGap?p_cod_ins=01TUFRRP&p_a_acc=2021&p_header=S&p_lang=EN , since AA 2019-2020) and in the mid-term plans to make the course compulsory and request PhD students to prepare a (simplified) Data Management Plan by the end of the first year.

TU-Darmstadt

Open Access actions: https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/service/elektronisches_publizieren/open_access_an_der_tu/index.en.jsp

TUDa has an Open Access Policy since August 2019, available in German only: https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/media/ulb/alter_webauftritt/pflicht_epublishing/pdf_11/OA-Policy_TUDarmstadt.pdf

- o Here is a DeepL translation:
 - o The Technische Universität (TU) Darmstadt is committed to the principles of freedom of research and teaching and open science. It advocates open research and teaching as well as social participation in the research results of its scientists and scholars. Taking into account the specifics of the disciplines and relevant quality criteria, publications produced at TU Darmstadt and research data and research results intended for publication should therefore be accessible and reusable under a free licence without restrictions as far as possible.
 - o In order to emphasise this goal, the TU Darmstadt has signed the "Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities " and supports initiatives that implement or further develop the objectives of the Berlin Declaration. The Presidential Board and the Senate of the TU Darmstadt see an important factor of successful and innovative teaching and research in the fact that members of the TU Darmstadt publish their research results freely and in open access and are enabled to freely and unhindered dispose of the results of their research.
 - o The Presidential Board will intensively promote Open Access, create incentive systems for Open Access publication and provide comprehensive advice and support to members of the TU Darmstadt on the issue of Open Access. Scientists and scholars at the TU Darmstadt should be enabled to exercise their vested right to free publication unhindered by outdated subscription and reputation models, so that their publications achieve maximum dissemination and the best reception conditions under strict scientific quality requirements and in accordance with the current state of the art. Furthermore, the Executive Board supports the better visibility of the research results and thus also the national and international networking of its scientists. The Executive Board will therefore develop sustainable and continuously updated measures for the implementation of Open Access, adapted to the respective framework conditions and disciplinary characteristics, and develop customised offers to support and advise members of the TU Darmstadt. This policy will be regularly evaluated with regard to new developments in the fields of Open Access and Open Science and adapted accordingly.
- Additionally there are Publication guidelines since February 2020, that supplements the OA policy with concrete specifications, recommendations and measures: https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/media/ulb/alter_webauftritt/pflicht_epublishing/pdf_11/publikationsrichtlinie.en.pdf
 - o Amongst others, TU Darmstadt
 - o „recommends providing all documents and all data, if possible, under a Creative Commons Licence (CC-BY) or Open Data Commons Licence (OCD-BY).“
- Both policies are far from being implemented properly in everyday life at TU Darmstadt, in fact both are unknown to many researchers.
- TUDa has an Open Access Officer, which is Prof. Dr. Andrea Rapp. She is in charge of coordinating the OA measures within the university.
- ULB (the library of TUDa) offers plentiful services to foster open access for publications, cf. https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/service/elektronisches_publizieren/startseite_ep_und_oa.en.jsp, beside others a well established OA repository (“TUprints”) and an “Open Access Check” for researchers and a secondary publication service that uses <https://dissem.in/> as well, a French platform we are collaborating with. Of course, there is a central fund for publication fees in OA journals. ULB experiments quite a lot with different models to finance OA publishing (“OA transformation deals”) since 3 years.
- In a third-party funded project (“OpenIng”) that tried to foster OA and OER in the Engineering Sciences we developed several of these services, cf. <http://www.opening-projekt.de/> (in German only)

- There is a lot of activities around Open Educational Resources (OER) incl. platforms for sharing them: https://www.e-learning.tu-darmstadt.de/dienstleistungen/rechtsfragen/oer_finden/index.de.jsp
- For research data management there are separate Guidelines from December 2015: https://www.tu-darmstadt.de/media/daa_responsives_design/03_forschung_medien/forschungsfoerderung_2/gute_wiss_praxis/Leitlinien_Forschungsdaten_2015.en.pdf
- These RDM guidelines are rather weak regarding open access, but at least they state: “The university encourages and supports sustainable safeguarding, and well-structured, open access to research data.”
- There is a specialised team on RDM called “TUdata” (bringing together staff from computing centre and library) that runs consulting services, trainings, a data repository called “TUdatalib”, a GitLab instance and a DMP-tool
- There is no CRIS at TU Darmstadt.

UGA

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<<https://www.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/recherche/ambition-strategie-partenaires/science-ouverte/science-ouverte-775832.kjsp>>

- Bibliothèques
- BAPSO <<https://bibliotheques.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/buchezvous/utilisez-et-alimentez-la-science-ouverte/>>

<<https://guide-hal.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/science-ouverte/science-ouverte-796444.htm>>

- Open edition:
- Centre Mersenne: <<https://www.centre-mersenne.org/>>
- UGA Editions: <<https://www.uga-editions.com/>>
- Data management:
- GRICAD: <<https://gricad.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/>> moyens de calcul et accompagnement gestion de données

<<https://gricad.gricad-pages.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/cellule-data-stewardship/web/>>

- PROGEDO (<<http://www.progedo.fr/>>): TGIR PROduction et Gestion des DONnées <<https://progedo.hypotheses.org/tag/grenoble>>
- Plateforme universitaire de données Grenoble Alpes (PUD-GA), plutôt pour pour les SHS <<https://www.msh-alpes.fr/plateformes/pud-ga>>
- <<https://www.dataacc.org/>> pour la recherche en physique/chimie
- MOOC:
- Reproducible Research:

<<https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/recherche-reproductible-principes-methodologiques-pour-une-science-transparente/>>

- Ethics: <<https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/ethique-de-la-recherche/>>
- Scientific integrity:

<<https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/integrite-scientifique-dans-les-metiers-de-la-recherche/>>

- Open Science coming soon: <<https://doranum.fr/2021/06/01/mooc-science-ouverte/>>
- Highlight on a lab: <<https://corelab.io/>> and the <<https://psysciacc.org/>>

ULisboa

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- In ULisboa the sharing open initiatives include two ways to ensure open access publication: Golden Way and Green Way. On the GOLDEN, the author publishes his article in an open-access journal, keeping all copyrights and the content is immediately available free of charge. On the GREEN, the author publishes his article in “traditional” journals and self-archives the authorized version, according to the publication or publisher policies, in the Repository of ULisboa. The Researcher decides where he wants to publish.
- The UL Institutional Repository ([Repositório.UL](#)) (*Repositório Institucional da Universidade de Lisboa*) collects, preserves and provides access to the research output of the university community and is part of the [RCAAP](#) Portal – the Portugal Open Access Research Repository (*Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal*).
The ULisboa Repository comprises several types of documents, in digital format, resulting from the research activities carried out at the University, namely: doctoral theses, masters dissertations, articles from national and international scientific journals, communications to congresses and conferences, among others, from all scientific areas existing at the University.
The Repository both meets the demand for maximum visibility and the need for proper curation and preservation of Portuguese research output for the future.
FCT has awarded key measure status to the filing of publications in any [RCAAP](#) repository in compliance with the Open Access Policy ([Política de Acesso Aberto](#)) in force since 2014.
- The ULisboa Search Service is a tool which allows for a broad search through all of ULisboa resources and those of its Schools, from a single point of access. The collections are stored at *b-on* (Online Knowledge Library), at the ULisboa Depository, and at all other systems, publications or subscriptions that each of the Schools have individually.
- In order to satisfy its users’ needs (students, professors, researchers and non-academic staff), the Universidade de Lisboa Libraries specialize in several themed domains, providing varied services, such as consultations and in-person book readings, periodicals, monographies, electronic and cartographical documents, book loans, access to data bases, and training.

UPC

- Open access:
 - Policies:

[Agreement no. 177 / 2014 of the Governing Council approving the allocation of PAR points solely for open access publications](#) → articles and conference papers must be in open access in order to be considered in UPC annual research assessment (embargo is considered; green route is supported)

[Agreement no. 171 / 2009 Open access institutional policy: access, visibility, impact and preservation of the academic production of the UPC on the internet](#) → UPC supports access, visibility, impact and preservation of all academic production.
 - Support:

The library gives support/advice to all UPC community in open access publishing.

- Open repositories:
 - Institutional repository:

[UPCommons](#) is the institutional repository. It hosts all types of academic production: pre-prints, post-prints, scientific articles, theses, researchdata, journals published by UPC units, congresses hosted at UPC teaching materials, bachelor's and master's theses, videos and heritage collections
 - Integration:

Upcommons is integrated with the UPC Current Research Information System and allows to show scientific outputs in [FUTUR. Website for the scientific production of UPC researchers](#)

- Open data:
 - Data Management Plans

UPC researchers can use an adapted version of [DMP tool](#) when they prepare their Data Management Plans for their projects. DMP are sharable.
 - Researchdata repository

For publishing and sharing big datasets, UPC researchers can also use the [Catalan researchdata repository](#)
 - Support:

The library gives support/advice to UPC researchers in researchdata publishing and sharing

- Open Science:
 - Webpage to help researchers to know more about Open science and increase open science practices during research. <https://biblioteca.upc.edu/en/investigadors/ciencia-oberta-upc>

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Open inviting initiatives

Aalto

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- A. **[Aalto University Open Science and Research Policy](#)**: Aalto University is committed to the opening of its physical infrastructures.
- B. **[Aalto University open physical infrastructure for knowledge production](#)**: Aalto University hosts high-level facilities for research, teaching and innovation, including unique nationally significant research infrastructures. These infrastructures are open for everyone. Some key cases:
- [OtaNano](#) is an open access research infrastructure, operated by Aalto University and VTT, and is available for academic and commercial users internationally. See [OtaNano open access policy](#) and [OtaNano open publishing and data policy](#).
 - [DesignFactory](#) is a platform for co-creation across disciplinary, organisational and even geographical boundaries. Design Factory brings together researchers from different disciplines to explore design, development, and innovation from a wide variety of disciplinary perspectives. The [facilities](#) are open to the students, researchers, start-ups and projects working and running at ADF.
- C. Pioneering open inviting initiatives promoted by researchers (bottom-up approach):
- [Citizen science practices and inter-disciplinary collaboration: \[Spatial Planning and Transportation Engineering Research Group\]\(#\)](#), School of Engineering: This research group has both practice- and science-based approach to engineering as collaborative development. Their research connects spatial planning and transportation engineering for developing new scientific knowledge needed in systemic understanding, problem-solving, and integrative planning and policy-making beyond sectoral boundaries, aimed at achieving human-centered living environments.
 - [Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research practices: \[CHEMARTS\]\(#\)](#) is a long-term strategic collaboration between two Aalto University schools, The School of Chemical Engineering (CHEM) and The School of Arts, Design and Architecture (ARTS). The main objective is to inspire students and researchers to explore biomaterials together and to create new concepts for the future use of cellulose and other biomaterials.
 - [Action research and participatory design practices: \[GroupX\]\(#\)](#), School of Arts, Design and Architecture. Research topics: shared resources and mixed use; sustainable development; life cycle thinking; co-design; user-centered design; value co-creation; communicative planning; parametric solutions; learning organizations and spaces.
 - [Open lab and transdisciplinary research: \[Biofilia\]\(#\)](#) is a joint collaboration between the School of Arts, Design and Architecture, the School of Chemical Engineering and the city of Espoo. It is a biological art unit. It offers a platform for trans-disciplinary research and education that aims to create cultural discussions and innovations around topics related to the manipulation of life and biological processes at a practical and theoretical level, including philosophical and ethical dimensions.
 - [Crowdsourcing practices: \[The Learning Environments Research Group \\(LeGroup\\)\]\(#\)](#), School of Science and School of Arts, Design and Architecture. Research involved in research, design, and development of New Media tools in the field of learning. The members of the group come from very different backgrounds covering education, computer science, and design.
 - [Action research and co-creation platform: \[Sim-lab\]\(#\)](#), School of Science. The core of SimLab is a virtual collaborative innovation environment for business processes. SimLab™ process simulation is a participative, facilitated business process discussion about the process activities and information flows in business networks. The simulation is an action research method that supports the co-creation of the networked processes and business model

These initiatives are grounded on Aalto's cross-cutting approaches of [radical creativity](#), [entrepreneurial mindset](#), and [solutions for sustainability](#).

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- Living lab - Citizen science: <https://openlivinglabdays.com/2019/06/17/citizen-science-living-labs-how-do-you-involve-citizen-scientists-in-your-living-lab-projects/>
- Stakeholder engagement in EU projects - Citizen Science. Research Support office.

Polito

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In PoliTO there are 11 Departments responsible of research activities in well defined scientific sectors. A significant transdisciplinary approach is ensured by the presence of several Interdepartmental Research Labs focusing on wide, transdisciplinary themes. See <https://www.polito.it/ricerca/centri/index.php?lang=en>

Some Departments (such as DIATI, DIGEP and DAUIN) organize **lunch seminars**, which are small talks organized around noon, usually once a month (e.g. every first Wednesday of the month) to spread the knowledge on specific matters in an informal and non-technical language.

There are no policies at institutional level about open collaborative tools, citizen science, etc. There might be some initiatives but these have never been monitored so far. This is a task we could arrange locally within WP6 activities.

To promote research and an (open) science culture, PoliTO organizes a few events – at central level - addressed to students and citizens such as:

- European Researchers' night
- National / regional science festivals, in particular Biennale della Tecnologia
<https://www.biennaletecnologia.it/every>
- Open lab days during which local audience visits the labs to experience in vivo how research is carried out at the local university
- Just the Woman I Am, an event organised yearly and held by the University Sport Center of Turin in partnership among others with Politecnico di Torino. It has been supporting gender equality, sport and the culture of well being, prevention and inclusion for the past 7 years. It consists of a 5 km run/ walk and the fee for the registration to the event is used for cancer research and gives each participant a pink t-shirt. (<https://www.torinodonna.it/home-2021-ing/>)
- Polito takes part to the International Open Access Week since 2018. In 2020 the programme proposed was in collaboration with other Italian Universities and it is available here https://www.biblio.polito.it/eventi_culturali/2020/oaweek2020
- YouTube Polito: Playlist Open Science:
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpBGG82odiy8dYJjLtGB-tg/playlists?view=50&sort=dd&shelf_id=9
- Further events may be found at https://www.biblio.polito.it/eventi_culturali/2020

TU-Darmstadt

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- TUDa participates in the „OA week“ since 2016: https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/service/elektronisches_publizieren/open_access_woche/open_access_woche.en.jsp
- There are several activities to open up TU Darmstadt to the public: https://www.tu-darmstadt.de/universitaet/mitten_in_der_gesellschaft/index.de.jsp, e.g.
 - Several public lecture series
- Guided Campus tours
- There are citizen science projects,
 - At ULB we had a project with geotagging of digitized old maps some years ago
 - Right now Andrea Rapp and ULB start a Citizen-Science-Project about Love Letters: https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/service/newsdetails_de_en_59200.en.jsp
 - There are more...

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- Fêtes de la science:

<<https://culture.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/menu-principal/culture-scientifique/evenements-conferences/fete-de-la-science/fete-de-la-science-675293.kjsp>>

- Cafés sciences et citoyens de l'agglomération grenobloise:

<<https://www.echosciences-grenoble.fr/communautes/cafe-sciences-et-citoyens-de-l-agglomeration-grenobloise>>

- Zététique (l'art du doute): <<https://cortecs.org/>>

<<https://www.echosciences-grenoble.fr/articles/zetetique-autodefense-intellectuelle-les-cours-de-richard-monvoisin>>

<<https://www.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/rayonnement/sciences-et-societe/les-cours-en-ligne-zetetique-et-autodefense-intellectuelle-/>>

ULisboa

Higher education institutions have the right and duty to liaise with society namely through knowledge transfer and dissemination activities and by actively promoting the economic value of scientific knowledge. The Interdisciplinary Thematic Networks (<https://www.ulisboa.pt/en/info/interdisciplinary-thematic-networks>) aim to mobilize ULisboa professors and researchers in specific areas of knowledge to increase the University's participation in international networks. Interdisciplinary Thematic Networks initiatives contribute to a better positioning of ULisboa for the smart specialization strategies (RIS3) within the Portugal 2020 framework and for Horizon 2020 societal challenges. Other initiatives include the development of strategic partnerships with organisations and institutions from the public, social and private sectors and the timely creation of Business Advisory Boards within the scope of each Thematic Interdisciplinary Network.

Universidade de Lisboa is committed to expand its internationalisation-related efforts into the Research, Development and Innovation domain, namely in the areas of redeAGRO, redeSAÚDE, redeMOV and redeMAR networks.

The ULisboa Colleges are non-organic work frames that incorporate programs of scientific research, technological innovation and education, which involve, professors and researchers from several Schools and research units, stakeholders and members of society. They are one way to promote cross-cutting initiatives, for the development of new cross-cutting areas of knowledge.

i) The Food, Farming and Forestry College (F3) is the catalyst for generating transdisciplinary knowledge in the areas of food, agriculture and forestry. As such, it triggers a holistic approach at promoting scientific and technological development, as well as at promoting teaching of innovation in the food and agro-forestry sectors, since it generates forward-looking public policy in the face of the multiple challenges with which human society has to cope on a national and international level. As an example of the diverse activities of the F3 are the Doctoral Degree in Sustainability Science, Reason-Resources, Food and Society, developed four years ago. The goal of the Doctoral Degree is to promote excellent and internationally competitive advanced training, transversely integrating solid and up-to-date knowledge for sustainable development. It is oriented to provide human resources with tools to understand and respond to current and future challenges that are posed to sustainability and result from understanding the interactions between global, natural and social systems to create new solutions and innovative policies.

The Team comprises: All ULisboa Faculties and Institutes - Faculty of Architecture, Faculty of Fine Arts, Faculty of Science, Faculty of Law, Faculty of Pharmacy, Faculty of Arts, Faculty of Medicine, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Faculty of Human Motricity, Faculty of Psychology, Institute of Social Sciences, Institute of Education, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, Superior Institute of Agronomy, Superior Institute of Social and Political Sciences, Superior Institute of Economics and Management and Superior Technical Institute.

ii) The Mind-Brain College aims at enhancing the transdisciplinary scientific activity and promoting the mind-brain connection and its social implications.

The Team comprises some ULisboa Faculties and Institutes: Faculty of Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, School of Arts and Humanities, Faculty of Medicine, Faculty of Psychology, Institute of Social Sciences and Técnico Lisboa.

iii) College on Polar and Extreme Environments ULisboa (POLAR2E) - Fostering interdisciplinary research in the frontiers of knowledge. The Polar2E of the ULisboa aims at creating synergies in areas such as the cryosphere, climate modelling, ecology, remote sensing, constructing in extreme environments, astrobiology and aerospace engineering, linking them to other research domains in the university. Problems such as sea-level rise, increasing extreme weather events, health and food safety or new geopolitical scenarios, have led to the strengthening of the concerns with the Polar regions at the national and international levels. Studying the complex dynamics of Polar regions implies enormous scientific, logistical and technological challenges, which can only be properly addressed

through interdisciplinary collaboration and international cooperation. Polar2E is a collaboration between IGOT – the Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, ISCSP – Institute of Social and Political Sciences, IST – The Instituto Superior Técnico and FCUL – The Faculty of Sciences, involving several research centres and laboratories.

iv) Tropical College (CTROP) is a transversal unit of the ULisboa, which aims to develop a transdisciplinary strategy at ULisboa with a view to solving societal challenges in tropical regions, and its vision to contribute to the reduction of inequalities between countries through the promotion of scientific and technological development, innovation and education in tropical regions.

Team: Faculty of Science (FC), Faculty of Pharmacy (FF), Institute of Molecular Medicine - Faculty of Medicine (IMM-FM), Faculty of Human Motricity (FMH), Higher Institute of Agronomy (ISA), Higher Technical Institute (IST), Institute of Education (IE), Faculty of Arts (FL), Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning (IGOT) and Faculty of Veterinary Medicine (FMV).

ULisboa takes part to the International Open Access Week.

The promotion of research and an open scientific culture in society, addressed to students and citizens, at ULisboa are highlighted (at central level, besides the initiatives at different schools), such as: European Researchers' night, Futurália, Summer at ULisboa, Ciência Viva at the Laboratory, Day Open by ULisboa for people over 23 years old.

The Summer at ULisboa to give High School students an opportunity to get to know and experiment its rhythm and its academic spirit. For a week, the students can actually be a vet, a dentist, an artist, an architect, a lawyer, a writer, a designer, a scientist, a coach, a geographer, an historian, a pharmacist, a biologist, a researcher, an agronomist, a geologist, a physicist, an economist, a manager, an engineer and much more. Throughout the scientific and sports activities, University students will be with the participants, showing them what university life is like and assisting them with tasks, answering their doubts and showing them around the premises.

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Citizen Science

- Portal:
This current year the UPC has launched the [UPC Citizen Science](#) Portal to invite citizen to participate in UPC research projects. The Portal also contains resources for researchers to help them in include citizen science initiatives/activities in their research projects.

Research Café:

- Sharing research between doctoral students
In order to help doctoral students UPC libraries organise Research Café:
The activity consists on organising an event where 4/5 doctoral students can share and discuss their research with other students and faculties. A poster presentation is prepared by each participant. After the event posters are published in [UPCommons](#) is the institutional repository.

